

Looking inside the Perchlorinated Trityl Radical/Metal Spinterface through Spectroscopy

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ABSTRACT We report on a spectroscopic multitechnique approach to study the metal/radical spinterface formed by a perchlorinated trityl radical derivative and either gold or silver. The spectroscopic fingerprint of their paramagnetic properties could be determined by comparison with their diamagnetic precursor and by DFT calculations. Thanks to the presented approach we could gain an unprecedented insight into the radical-metal interaction and how this latter perturbs

the spin polarization and consequently the magneto-electronic properties of the radical adlayer. The knowledge of the factors influencing the spinterface is an essential tool towards the tailoring of the properties of spin-based electronic devices.

TEXT.

Organic radical derivatives,¹ *i.e.* metal-free molecular derivatives with an unpaired electron spin, traditionally known as key players in protein chemistry² and as tectons of multifunctional materials,³ have been recently shown as suitable components of spin-based molecular electronic (molecular spintronics) devices.⁴⁻⁸ Indeed, their chemical synthetic flexibility, absent in inorganic materials traditionally used in spintronics,^{9,10} allows to engineer specific network structures¹¹ and their magneto-electronic properties by tuning the strength of the interaction with the surface.¹²⁻¹⁴ This latter is indeed a crucial point for the actual implementation of molecular spintronics in devices since realistic large-scale applications require the fabrication of supported architectures, which assure well-ordered, reproducible and easy-grown structures. Nevertheless, the formation of chemical bonds between the deposited radical molecular derivative and the anchoring metal may change the electronic structure of the molecule and thus the spin polarization (*i.e.* the magnetic properties). Additionally, the nature of the chemical bonds at the interface governs the spin-injection mechanism into the molecule. Consequently the understanding of the electronic and magnetic properties of the organic radical-metal interface is mandatory towards the realization of operating spintronic devices. Organic radical-metal interfaces can be considered as spinterfaces, a term initially coined for interfaces with a spin-dependence density of states,¹⁵ since such a property can be attained in these interfaces under a very large magnetic field or at moderate magnetic fields but very low temperatures. Standard

microscopy techniques, even though important to visualize the supramolecular arrangements of nano-objects on metal substrates, may not be sufficient to characterize the modifications of the electronic structure induced at the spinterface. Therefore we herein present a multitechnique spectroscopic approach, based on synchrotron and laboratory emission and absorption techniques (e.g. valence band and core level photoemission spectroscopies, VB PES and PES; inverse photoemission spectroscopy, IPS; angle-resolved near-edge X-ray absorption spectroscopy, NEXAFS), supported by *ab initio* simulations to investigate the spinterfaces formed by a perchlorinated trityl radical derivative (tri-*p*-carboxy polychlorotriphenylmethyl radical, PTMTC, Figure 1a) and two noble metals, Au(111) and Ag(111). As it will be discussed, we have been able to elucidate the effects of the strength of the molecule-substrate interaction on the electronic properties and on the preservation of the paramagnetism of the first molecular layer. The molecular orbitals and the structure of PTMTC appear differently perturbed on the two substrates: The strong electronegativity of the chlorine substituents on the PTMTC plays a major role on Ag(111), leading to a strong interaction and hybridization of the molecular orbitals with formation of an interface molecular state with quenching of the paramagnetic character of the layer, while on Au(111), the weaker radical-metal interaction has no effect neither on the electronic nor on the paramagnetic properties, in agreement with what hypothesized in a previous work.¹⁶ Our results reveal that the chemical composition of the organic radical layer and hence the type of interface bonding between the molecule and the metal substrate play a crucial role in the finely tuning of the interfacial electronic and paramagnetic properties.^{13, 17-21}

The tri-*p*-carboxy polychlorotriphenylmethyl radical derivative (PTMTC, Figure 1a) is a stable and persistent molecule with an open shell electronic configuration. Its stability comes from the bulky chlorine atoms in the 6 *ortho* positions (C₄ and C_{4'}, Fig. 1a) that protect the central radical

carbon atom (C_6 , Figure 1a) from unwanted reactions that could lead to the loss of the radical character. Additionally, the PTMTC shows a high thermal stability that allows sublimation under ultra-high vacuum conditions (UHV), as we demonstrated in a previous work¹⁶ where thin films of PTMTC were prepared on Au(111) and studied by scanning tunneling microscopy (STM). Herein, we instead used a multitechnique approach to identify the radical spectroscopic fingerprint of multilayered films prepared by UHV sublimation by comparison with the PTMTC diamagnetic precursor (α H-PTMTC, Figure 1a). As it is shown in Figure 1a, the C1s core level PE spectra of the thin films of PTMTC¹⁶ (in red, Figure 1a) and of its diamagnetic precursor (in black, Figure 1a), show several components related to the different C atoms. The band at binding energy (BE) of -283.7 eV can be attributed to the central C_6 atom (Figure 1a) on the basis of the comparison with the C1s spectra of the non-radical derivative, where it is absent (Supplementary Figure 1). DFT calculations confirmed the assignments of the BE of the other carbon atoms (Supplementary Table 1). The Cl 2p and O1s PE spectra (Supplementary Figure 2) are, as expected, similar for both PTMTC and α H-PTMTC. Valence band (VB) PE spectra of PTMTC (Figure 1b, red) and α H-PTMTC (Figure 1b, black), instead, show a striking difference: A molecular state at -1.6eV is present in the case of the radical derivative and not in the case of the diamagnetic precursor. Its absence in this latter case, together with the paramagnetic character of the radical film found by electron spin resonance (ESR)¹⁶, confirms that this state is attributable to the single occupied molecular orbital (SOMO). The empty counterpart of this molecular state (the single unoccupied molecular orbital, SUMO) is indeed observed in IPS (Figure 1c) and C K edge NEXAFS spectra (Figure 1d) of thin films of PTMTC. This result is valuable since the final state in the two techniques is different, due to the presence of the core hole in absorption.²²

All the assignments of the molecular orbitals are confirmed by the Density of States (DOS) of DFT-PBE calculations (Figure 1c) that find a magnetic moment of 1 Bohr magneton per molecule. This framework provides only a partial description of the magnetic properties of paramagnetic complexes, due to the difficulty of modeling exchange and electron correlation phenomena using effective one-electron potentials. IPS (PES) represent a negative (positive) ion state while absorption spectroscopy an excited neutral state containing an electron-hole pair. Special care must be taken in comparing PES and IPS with DFT DOS, due to the different final state effects,²³ Taken that into account, it is possible to extract from the comparison a coherent description and to rationalize important information. Interestingly, on the basis of the comparison of inverse photoemission (IPS) spectra and of the C K and Cl L 2,3 edges NEXAFS (Supplementary Figure 3) the SUMO is mainly formed by C contribution with a faint contribution from Cl detectable at the Cl L2,3 edge. This indication, confirmed also by partial DOS, implies that the spin does not only reside only on the central C₆ atom but it is delocalized on the whole molecule, as it was already suggested as a consequence of the out-of-plane torsion of the three phenyl rings caused by the bulky chlorine atoms in C₄ and C₄.²⁴

Figure 1. a) (Left) C1s PE spectra of thin films of PTMTC radical (red) and its diamagnetic precursor (α H-PTMTC, black). The molecular structures of both compounds with the carbon numbering are on the right. b) Extended Valence Band PE spectra of PTMTC (red) and its non-radical precursor (black). c) Combined PES (grey) and IPS (black) spectra of thin films of PTMTC. The SOMO and its empty counterpart SUMO are clearly seen and show an energy distance of $2.3 + 0.2$ eV. The spectra are compared with the calculated Density of States (DOS) of the spin up (red shadow) and spin down (blue shadow) of an isolated molecule. d) NEXAFs C K edge of non-radical α -PTMTC thin film (blue) and PTMTC thin film (red).

In order to address the PTMTC-metal interface and understand how the electronic structure of the PTMTC is affected by the interaction with the surface we deposited the PTMTC as

submonolayer (subML) and monolayer (ML) on Au(111) and Ag(111). On Au(111), the C1s and Cl2p core level PES do not show significant changes (Figure 2a, black), while the O1s PES suggests a partial deprotonation of the carboxylic groups (Figure 2b, black). By recording the Au4f core level PE in surface sensitive mode, we can indeed discard a strong interaction of the PTMTC with the gold substrate (Supplementary Figure 4). NEXAFS spectra (Figure 2c) show the transition to the SUMO orbital at 282.5 eV and VB PES (Figure 2d) show a feature attributable to the SOMO, at all the investigated coverages, with a BE that decreases with the increase going from subML to ML regime, approaching the value of the SOMO in thin films.

Figure 2. a) C1s (left) and Cl2p (right) PE spectra of PTMTC on Au(111), black, and Ag(111), grey, at 1ML coverage (top) and 0.5ML coverage (bottom). The intensity of the lower BE in the Cl 2p spectra is about 30% and, taking into account the photoelectron signal attenuation of the interface Cl atoms due to the electron mean free path it is indeed compatible with the suggested DFT optimized geometry. b) O1s PE spectra of PTMTC thin film (continuous dark blue line) and as 1ML on Au(111), in black, and on Ag(111), in grey. c) C K edge NEXAFs of 1L PTMTC on Au(111) and Ag(111). The SUMO is clearly indicated. d) Left: VB maximum of PTMTC thin film and as 1ML on Au(111) and on Ag(111). Clean Au(111) and clean Ag(111) are reported for the sake of comparison. Right: evolution of the work function with the coverage for PTMTC on Au(111), top, and Ag(111), bottom. PE spectra at different coverages on Au(111) and Ag(111) are shown in Supplementary Figure 5.

The change in the SOMO position is accompanied by the change in the work-function (Figure 2d, inset) with the coverage.²⁵ The WF decreases till a minimum at -0.34 eV in correspondence of 0.5 ML, and then it undergoes a slight and continuous increase for higher coverages. The WF trend is compatible with a non-covalent interaction of the PTMTC islands on Au(111) till 0.5ML with the prevalence of the pillow effect,²⁶ hence supporting the recently suggested hypothesis¹⁶. The slight increase observed for coverages higher than 0.5ML implies that additional intermolecular interactions take place at higher coverages. The observed changes in WF are in qualitative agreement with DFT results that show a slight but not negligible reduction of WF (-20 meV) in the case of Au substrate (Figure 2d, inset). Therefore the collected data suggest a scenario so far not reported for radicals on Au(111): We can discard the presence of any hybridization and hence of any change in the electronic and paramagnetic structure at the

spinterface. Interestingly enough, not even at coverages lower than 0.5ML there is an effect on the electronic and paramagnetic structure.

Confirmation of the given interpretation of the experimental data comes from DFT-PBE calculations extended to 1 ML PTMTC on Au(111). For the study of the molecule-substrate interfaces, two configurations have been examined: One with PTMTC standing almost vertical (small tilted angle) and one where the molecule lies horizontally flat. According to the optimized geometry (Figure 3, left panel), the PTMTC is at a small tilting angle with the surface and loses a -H atom on the COOH moiety, in agreement with the O1s core level spectra. The results of electronic structure calculations show that on Au(111) PTMTC maintains all the features of isolated molecule (Supplementary Figure 6). In particular, both the SOMO and SUMO survive (as confirmed by NEXAFS) as result of a weak interaction with the metal and the calculated magnetic moment maintains the molecular value (1 Bohr magneton). The central atom C₆ adsorbed on Au maintains the same Löwdin charge (3.95e) and atomic spin polarization (charge up – charge down = 0.65) as the pristine molecule. Therefore, on Au(111) a weak interaction mainly drawn by dipole interaction (and possibly by redistribution of the charge in the molecules) takes place with a slight SOMO-SUMO energy separation shift.¹⁶ The screening, excitonic and polarization effects can result in a shift of the frontier orbital features. These contributions have been evaluated for a plethora of organics layers, including paramagnetic copper phtalocyanine derivatives, resulting in a shift in the range of 0.1-0.4 eV in the combined PES-IPS spectra.^{23a}

Figure 3. Partial DOS for PTMTC adsorbed on Au(111) (left) and on Ag(111) (right) with the side views of the structure of PTMTC on Au(111) (yellow) and on Ag(111) (light blue) substrates and the electronic charge profile in the two cases. For Au(111) a depletion (pillow effect) is obtained, while in Ag interface an increase of charge takes place at interfaces. Positive curves and negative curves indicate the spin up and spin down contributions. The Au/Ag contributions to DOS are not shown for clarity. The zero energy reference is set to the Fermi level of each hybrid interface.

When using Ag(111) as substrate, a different scenario appears. Both C 1s and Cl 2p PES (Figure 2a) indicate a strong interaction of the PTMTC with the metal: in C1s core level spectra at both 0.5 and 1ML the band at BE of -283.7 eV, attributed to the central C₆ atom, is unambiguously suppressed. This cannot be attributed to fragmentation of the molecule since in both NEXAFS (Figure 2c) and VB PES (Figure 2d) occupied and empty molecular orbitals, respectively, remain clearly distinguishable. From the Cl2p spectra another striking difference arises: Two doublets are observed, with the one at lower binding energy being about 30% of the

other one. The presence of two doublets is compatible with the presence of two sets of chlorine: one facing the vacuum and one, at lower BE, facing the metal and hence interacting strongly with it. A strong interaction with the metal finds confirmation in C K edge NEXAFS (Figure 2c) taken on 1 monolayer where the transition to the SUMO orbital at 282.5 eV appears quenched and broadened. Accordingly, VB PES spectra (Figure 2d) show that the peak below the Fermi level (at 1.8 eV) is detected for all the investigated coverages but its BE remains unchanged, differently from what happens on Au(111), thus remarking that it is an interface state. In agreement with this finding we observe a continuous increase in the work function as result of a strong interaction with the metal. The changes in WF (Figure 2d) are again in qualitative agreement with DFT results that show a WF increase of about +0.02 eV in the case of Ag. Therefore our results indicate a strong interaction between the metal surface and the molecule and a charge transfer from the Ag(111) to the radical that leads to the filling of the SUMO and hence to the appearance at the interface of a new hybridized state whose energy does not change with the coverage. The hybridization at the interface has been reported in the case of 1,3,5-phenyl verdazyl radicals derivatives on Au(111), where a Kondo resonance could be seen by scanning tunneling spectroscopy.¹³ In the present case, we suggest that the chlorine atoms strengthen the interaction with the Ag(111) substrate leading to a quenching of the SUMO, as well as the suppression of the C₆ component in the C1s XPS spectra. DFT-PBE calculations performed for 1 ML PTMTC on Ag(111) are in full agreement with the spectroscopic data. Analogously to what done on Au(111), two configurations -with PTMTC standing almost vertical (small tilted angle) and horizontally flat- were examined. In the case of Ag (Figure 3, right panel) the molecule adsorbs almost parallel to the surface, maximizing the number of Cl-Ag interaction, as could also be inferred from the relative intensity of the two doublets in the Cl

2p spectra (Supplementary Figure 7). The results of electronic structure calculations show an overall modification of the molecular-projected DOS over the entire energy range, with respect to the gas phase reference. The most evident change involves the molecular sharp SUMO peak, which is now largely broadened across the Fermi level becoming partially occupied, with a calculated magnetic moment quenched to 0.3 Bohr magneton. The Löwdin charge of C₆ increases its atomic value (4.12e), and the spin polarization is reduced to 0.14, this being a clear signature of a metal-to-molecule charge transfer and the formation of direct chemical bonds mediated by the chlorine. The quenching of the SUMO is calculated also for higher energy geometry, *i.e* with the molecule tilted with respect to the surface, like in the configuration on Au(111), and with a lower number of Cl atoms in contact with Ag substrate, supporting the existence of a stronger interaction in the case of silver. The calculations confirm an overall charge transfer from the metal to the molecule, as also proposed on the basis of PES and NEXAFS: the interface state detected in the VB PES is indeed well reproduced by our calculations at about -1.9 eV, see IH in Figure 3. This state derives from the hybridization of Ag s-band with the pristine π -like spin-unpolarized HOMO-1 state of PTMTC, which has a relevant contribution from Cl atoms (see Supplementary 5). We can thus conclude that on Ag(111) the molecular orbitals, are deformed, shifted and the relevant features broadened, emerging as new hybrid interface states.¹⁶ We note however that, even though the formation of chemical bonds at the interface may reduce the energy barrier for electron injection, this is not necessarily an advantage for spin injection: the electronic structure redistribution induced the presence of Ag substrate washes out the magnetic polarization of PTMTC, vanishing its application in spintronic devices.

The spinterface between a trityl radical derivative and either gold or silver has been investigated by means of a multitechnique spectroscopic approach to gain insight on the perturbation caused by the metal substrate to the spin polarization. While on Au(111) the radical/metal interaction is weak and no loss in the spin polarization takes place,²⁷ on Ag(111) the Cl atoms are responsible for the formation of Ag-Cl bonds that lead to a charge redistribution with broadening of the SUMO that becomes an interfacial state whose energy coincides with the one of the Fermi level. The experimental evidences are confirmed by calculations that clearly indicate that the SOMO-SUMO energy difference decreases and that the SUMO lies across the Fermi Level and the paramagnetism of the radical results strongly quenched. The reported results shed light on the charge redistribution at the metal-organic interfaces on the molecular scale towards the understanding of the energy level alignment and the transport processes at the spinterface with huge implication on the nanomagnetism and the knowledge of the parameters to be taken into account towards the actual implementation of organic radicals in spintronic devices.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information. Synthesis of PTMTC radical.²⁸ Experimental conditions used in spectroscopic studies. Procedures for theoretical calculations. C1s core level spectra (C1s, Cl2p and O1s) of PTMTC and its no radical precursor α H-PTMTC and assignments of C1s core level based on DFT calculations; Comparison between IPS and element sensitive NEXAFS data (C K edge and Cl L2,3 edge) of PTMTC films; PES Au 4f core level for clean and subML coverages of PTMTC on Au(111) taken at 350 eV of photon energy; PE spectra at different coverages on Au(111) and Ag(111); Spin-unrestricted density of states of PTMTC isolated molecule and isosurface plot of representative molecular orbitals; Description of the Cl2p core level spectra for

PTMTC on Ag(111) and coverage dependence. This material is available free of charge via the Internet at <http://pubs.acs.org>.

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Author Contributions

The manuscript was written through contributions of all authors. All authors have given approval to the final version of the manuscript. V. M., M.P. and J. V. conceived and designed the experiments; M. G., I. A., R. O., A. V., V.M and M.P performed the experiments; V. M. and M.P. analyzed the data; V. M., A. C., M. P and J. V. co-wrote the paper.

Competing financial interests. The authors declare not competing financial interests.

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ABBREVIATIONS

VB PES, valence band photoemission; PES, core level photoemission; IPS, inverse photoemission; NEXAFS, angle-resolved near-edge X-ray absorption spectroscopy; PTMTC, tri-*p*-carboxy polychlorotriphenylmethyl radical.

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Graphical TOC

A spectroscopic multitechnique approach providing insights into the radical-metal spinterface of a monolayer of perchlorinated trityl radicals deposited on gold and on silver surfaces is presented.